

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v201 Solar Gain in Winter

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Abstract

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization (BESOO) is a system of online internet programs that calculates temperatures, energy, and other parameters for various cases and conditions based on input values.

The current version (201) includes solar radiation on the outside walls of the building and allows selection of the building orientation every 22.5 degrees.

The program calculates temperatures of the outside wall layers and the air temperature in the room at a constant ambient air temperature. In addition, the program calculates TTC based on the input data.

This work includes examples of the application of BESOO to determine room air temperature without space heating or air conditioning at various ambient air temperatures and thermal insulation thicknesses.

The simulation shows that the maximum temperature drop for an uninsulated apartment is from 20°C to 14.2°C in 10 days in winter, while for well-insulated walls is up to 16.9°C.

The program may be useful for selecting optimum building design, especially the location and thickness of insulation and thermal mass such as a concrete layer.

The online internet program according to this work is available on nowagreen.com/BESO/201 (free, no login required).

Glossary

AbF	absorption coefficient of solar energy on building wall [1]
Ave	Average
CFD	conversion factor from global radiation on horizontal surface to selected tilt angle and direction [8]
COP	Coefficient of Performance of air conditioning
dir	outside wall direction
dtau	time period of the integration = integration interval [sec]
H	height of the room [m]
kWhTh	kilo-Watt-hour thermal = kWh _e * COP – actual heat (+) or cool (-) supplied to the room by air conditioning
kWh _e	kilo-Watt-hour electric – electricity consumption by air conditioning [kWh]
L	length of outside wall [m]
Ref	reference
SE	solar global radiation on horizontal surface [W/m ²]
SE _d	solar radiation on vertical surface in direction dir [W/m ²]
SE _o	solar energy absorbed by outside wall [Ws/m ²]
T _a	ambient (outside) air temperature [°C]
T _{room}	room air temperature [°C]
TTC	Thermal Time Constant, hours [4]
We	Watt electric – electricity consumption of air conditioning [Wh/hr]
W _{th}	Watt thermal = We * COP – actual heat (+) or cool (-) supplied to the room by air conditioning

Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Energy is expressed in Joule, Ws, or kWh

$$W = J / \text{sec}$$

$$kW = 1,000 J / \text{sec}$$

$$kWh = 1,000 J * 3,600 \text{ sec/hr} = 3,600,000 J$$

Air conditioning electricity power (for cooling or heating) is expressed in [We] (W electric):

$$We = Wth / COP$$

$$kWe = kWth / COP$$

COP Coefficient of Performance of the air conditioning system

- o heat transfer through conduction (heat flow) is expressed in Joule/second

$$1 J/s = 1 W$$

- o change in thermal mass of a layer is expressed in Joules

$$1 J = 1 Ws$$

$$1 kWh_{th} = 3,600,000 J$$

kWh_{th} kWh thermal, in difference to kWh electric [kWh_e]

Time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST is not considered.

Building and the Apartment

In this version, the calculations are for the entire apartment and not for individual rooms; the entire apartment is considered one room.

It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring apartments is the same as in the tested apartment.

Chart 1 - Building and apartment

Energy Calculations

In general, energy calculations in this simulation are related to 2 aspects:

- conduction heat transfer through the outside wall layers
- changes in the thermal mass of the outside wall layers

Both cases involve "temperature difference" (dt , ΔT , Δt). There is a different meaning of dt (Δt) in the case of conduction heat transfer and the case of change in the thermal mass of the layer.

In the case of conduction, dt (Δt) is the difference between the temperature at the starting point of the heat flow and the endpoint.

In case of a change in the thermal mass of the layer, dt (Δt) is the change of the layer temperature at the same point (in this work at the center of the layer).

To distinguish between conduction and thermal mass, the energy related to the conduction heat flow will be indicated in this work as "Q" and the change in the thermal mass of the layer as "E".

The radiation heat transfer (like radiation from outside walls to outer space at night) is not included in this version.

Conduction Heat Transfer Between Layers

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 1 - Heat transfer through multi-layer building element

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

- Q overall heat transfer through multi-layer building element (like few layers of outside wall) [W]
- U overall coefficient of heat transfer [W/m²,°C]
- A area normal to the flow (like outside wall total area) [m²]
- ($t_{hi} - t_{low}$) temperature difference between the start point of the heat flow and the end point [°C]

Changes in Thermal Mass of a Layer

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 2 - Change in layer's temperature

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * d\tau / MC$$

$$Q_{in} = q_{in} * A$$

$$Q_{out} = q_{out} * A$$

$$MC = M * c_p$$

$$M = A * Th * Rho$$

- A area of the layer [m²]
- c_p specific heat at constant pressure [J/kg,°C]
- dt temperature increase of the layer [°C] in period $d\tau$
- $d\tau$ integration interval [sec]
- M mass of the layer [kg]
- q_{in} energy flow into the layer [W/m²]
- q_{out} energy flow out from the layer [W/m²]

Rho density of the material of the layer (like concrete) [kg/m³]
 Th thickness of the layer [m]

Outside Wall Layers

In this program, the heat flow is from outside the building to inside. In cases where the heat flow is in the opposite direction, the value of the conductive heat flow [Q] will be negative.

Table 1 - Outside wall layers

Layer #	Layer	Material
Outside air		
0	Outside laminar layer	
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base
2	Outside insulation	PS
3	Central layer	Concrete
4	Inside insulation	PS
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster
r	Inside laminar layer	
Room air		

Table 2 - Conduction heat flow between layers

Q	from	to	From	to
Qo1	Outside air	Center of layer 1	Ta	To1
Qo3	Center of layer 1	Center of layer 3	To1	To3
Qo5	Center of layer 3	Center of layer 5	To3	To5
QoR	Center of layer 5	Room air	To5	Troom

Table 3 - Change in thermal energy of outside wall layers

Layer #	Material	E	Qin	Qout	Temperature
1	Stones + Cement Base	$E_{o1} = Q_{o1} + SE_{o1} - Q_{o3}$	$Q_{o1} + SE_{o1}$	Qo3	To1
3	Concrete	$E_{o3} = Q_{o3} - Q_{o5}$	Qo3	Qo5	To3
5	Gypsum Plaster	$E_{o5} = Q_{o5} - Q_{oR}$	Q5	QoR	To5

Change in Thermal Energy of Outer Layer (Layer 1)

Calculations of thermal energy of room air are based on Formula 2:

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * dtau / MC$$

$$Q_{in} = Q_{o1} + SE_o$$

$$Q_{out} = Q_{o3}$$

Formula 3 - Outer layer (Layer 1) temperature change

$$dt = (Q_{o1} + SE_o - Q_{o3}) * dtau / MC1$$

dt	temperature increase of Layer 1 in $dtau$ period [°C]
Q_{in}	thermal energy entering Layer 1 [W]
Q_{out}	thermal energy leaving Layer 1 [W]
$dtau$	integration interval [sec]
Q_{o1}	conduction heat flow from outside air to the center of outer layer (Layer 1) [W]
Q_{o3}	conduction heat flow from the center of outer layer (Layer 1) to the center of central layer (Layer 3) [W]
SE_o	solar energy absorbed by outer layer (Layer 1) [W]
$MC1$	MC of Layer 1 [J/°C,m ²]

Solar Energy Absorbed by Outer Layer of Outside Wall (Layer 1)

Formula 4 - Solar energy absorbed by outer layer of outside wall (Layer 1)

$$SE_o = SE_{odir1} + SE_{odir2}$$

$$SE_{odir1} = SE * A_{o1} * CF_{dir1} * AbF$$

$$SE_{odir2} = SE * A_{o2} * CF_{dir2} * AbF$$

SE_o	solar energy absorbed by Layer 1, W
SE_{odir1}	solar energy absorbed by part 1 of outside wall Layer 1 in direction $dir1$ (like East), W
SE_{odir2}	solar energy absorbed by part 2 of outside wall Layer 1 in direction $dir2$ (like South), W
SE	solar global radiation on horizontal surface, W/m ² [6]

$Ao1$	area of part 1 of the external wall in direction $dir1$ (like East)
$Ao2$	area of part 2 of the external wall in direction $dir2$ (like South)
$CFdir$	conversion factor from global radiation on horizontal surface to selected tilt angle and direction [8]
AbF	solar absorption coefficient, absorption coefficient of solar radiation on building wall [1]

$$AbF = 0.53 \quad [1]$$

The solar absorption coefficient (AbF) depends on many factors and its determination is much beyond the scope of this work. The current version applies $AbF=0.53$ as in the original BESO program [1].

In this version, the global solar radiation (SE) is the same every day as on 23 December 2024 in Jerusalem (3,650 Wh/m²,day) and the $CFdir$ is for December only [8].

Change in Thermal Energy of Room Air

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 5 - Temperature change in room air [7]

$$dt = QoR * dtau / MCa$$

dt	temperature increase of the air in the room in the $dtau$ period [°C]
QoR	conduction heat flow from the center of the inner layer of the outside wall to the room [W]
$dtau$	integration interval [sec]

$$MCa = Ma * cpa$$

$$Ma = Va * RhoA$$

MCa	thermal mass of the air in the room [J/°C]
Ma	mass of the air in the room [kg]
Va	volume of the air in the room [m ³]
$RhoA$	density of the air in the room [kg/m ³]
cpa	specific heat of the air in the room [J/kg,°C]

$$c_{pa} = 1,007 \text{ J/kg,}^\circ\text{C} \quad [7]$$

$$RhoA = 1.205 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad [7]$$

Building Energy Simulation

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 6 - Conduction heat transfer through outside wall layers (Q), W/°C [7]

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

$$Q_{o1} = UA_{o1} * (T_a - T_{o1})$$

$$Q_{o3} = UA_{o3} * (T_{o1} - T_{o3})$$

$$Q_{o5} = UA_{o5} * (T_{o3} - T_{o5})$$

$$Q_{oR} = UA_{oR} * (T_{o5} - T_{room})$$

Formula 7 - Simulation of temperature

In the programming language, the simulation of the temperature has the following form:

$$T_{new} = T_{last} + dt$$

T_{new}	new temperature of the body [°C]
T_{last}	last temperature of the body [°C]
dt	temperature increase of the body [°C] in period $d\tau$

BESOO Simulation Examples – Insulation Thickness

The following examples are for a constant ambient air temperature of 10°C. The initial room air temperature is 20°C. The apartment orientation is East and South. Solar radiation is the same every day as on 23 December 2024 in Jerusalem.

Table 4 - Input data for all examples

fix Ta	10	°C
initial room air temperature	20	°C
orientation	E, S	
Solar radiation day, Jerusalem	23-Dec-24	W/m2
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100	m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200	m
inner insulation layer (4) thickness	0.000	m
inner plaster layer (5) thickness	0.015	m

Table 5 - Outer insulation thickness

outer insulation - layer 2	TTC, hr	Troom after 1 day, °C	Troom after 5 days, °C	Troom after 10 days, °C	Troom Min, °C
0 cm	25.3	+17.96	+16.20	+16.17	+14.24
2 cm	109.61	+19.45	+17.35	+16.37	+15.99
3 cm	151.82	+19.59	+17.83	+16.74	+16.50
4 cm	194.07	+19.68	+18.17	+17.08	+16.92

Chart 2 - Insulation thickness – room air temperature in 10 days, °C

Website

Chart 3 - [BESOO online simulation input page \[9\]](https://nowagreen.com/BESO/201/)

Nowagreen Global Warming Database
 Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO page 201, v201.01
 Change of room air temperature with time
 Fix ambient air temperature, no heat or AC, outside walls only
 Solar radiation in Jerusalem, December only

The outer insulation (layer 2) and the inner insulation (layer 4) is Polystyrene Foam (PS) - 0.0320 W/m,°C thermal conductivity.
 If other thermal insulation is applied, the insulation thickness may be corrected to the PS equivalent. For example, insulation with 10% higher conductivity should be submitted to the following input table with 10% lower thickness.

choose direction of part 1:

choose direction of part 2:

fix ambient air temperature	10 °C
initial room air temperature	20 °C
room height	2.65 m
outside wall part 1 length	10 m
outside wall part 2 length	10 m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100 m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040 m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200 m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015 m

Chart 4 - [BESOO online simulation results page \[9\]](https://nowagreen.com/BESO/201/201.php)

simulation completed, simulation time: 1 sec

simulation results:

31/05/2025 20:34:50 GMT			
nowagreen.com BESOO page 201, v201.01 No Heat/AC, Fix Ta, Fix Initial Troom, Solar radiation in Jerusalem in December only, Outside walls only			
page	no Heat/AC	201	
URL	https://nowagreen.com/BESO/101		
Version	v	201.01	
Integration Interval	dtau	1	sec
Thermal Time Constant	TTC	194.07	hours
Fix Ambient Temperature	Ta	10	°C
Initial Room Air Temperature	TroomStart	20	°C
Last Room Air Temperature	Troom	17.42	°C

This simulation program is based on research "Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO" by Joseph Nowarski and G. L. Esterson, presented at First Joint Conference of International Simulation Societies, 22-25 August 1994, ETH Zurich, Switzerland.

cite this page:
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